

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIPOSITIVE SILVER WITH PYRIDINE CARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART III. ARGENTIC COMPOUNDS OF PYRIDINE TRICARBOXYLIC ACIDS

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In continuation of the previous work on silver(II) complexes of pyridine mono- and dicarboxylic acids it has now been possible to prepare the argentic complexes of some of the pyridine tricarboxylic acids, namely pyridine-2 : 3 : 6-, -2 : 4 : 5-, and -2 : 4 : 6-carboxylic acids.

Argentio complexes of all the three acids were obtained by the persulphate oxidation of silver nitrate in presence of the acid concerned. The argentic complex of pyridine-2 : 3 : 6-tricarboxylic acid forms a very unstable green compound. Pyridine-2 : 4 : 6-tricarboxylic acid gave two differently coloured complex salts, one chocolate and the other black, whereas the colour of argentic complex of pyridine-2 : 4 : 5-tricarboxylic acid is orange.

The properties of these complexes are more or less similar to those of the mono- and dicarboxylic acid complexes. These are possibly represented by monomeric structure like that of argentic picolinate. X-ray powder photographs show that the black and chocolate modifications of the argentic complex of collidinic acid (2 : 4 : 6-acid) differ in their crystal structure. A consideration of the properties of the argentic complexes of pyridine mono-, di- and tri-carboxylic acids indicates that the order of their stability can be represented as follows :

Complex (mono) > Complex (di) > Complex (tri).

In our previous communications (*this Journal*, 1956, 33, 503 ; 1957, 34, 207) an account of the preparation, properties and constitution of the silver^{II} complexes with pyridine mono- and dicarboxylic acids has been given. We have now been able to prepare and study some of the argentic complexes with pyridine tricarboxylic acids, which form the subject matter of the present paper. Of the six different pyridine tricarboxylic acids, as shown below, argentic complexes with three of them have been studied, namely with (III), (IV) and (V).

2 : 3 : 4-acid
(I)

2 : 3 : 5 acid
(II)

2 : 3 : 6 acid
(III)

2 : 4 : 5-acid
(IV)

2 : 4 : 6-acid
(V)

3 : 4 : 5-acid
(VI)

Pyridine -3 : 4 : 5-, -2 : 3 : 4- and -2 : 3 : 5-tricarboxylic acids were not available for the present and, hence, the preparation and properties of their argentic complexes could not

be studied. The other three acids (mentioned before) gave bipoisitive silver complexes by persulphate oxidation of silver nitrate in presence of the acid concerned. The silver^{II} complex of 2:3:6-tricarboxylic acid of pyridine, however, forms a very unstable green compound, which decomposes even when kept in a vacuum desiccator at 5°, though it remains unchanged in the cold reaction mixture in the presence of an excess of sodium persulphate solution. Pyridine-2:4:6-tricarboxylic acid, like dipicolinic acid, gave two different complex salts, one chocolate and the other black. The colour of silver^{II} complex with 2:4:5 tricarboxylic acid of pyridine is orange.

The properties of these compounds are more or less similar to those of the mono-carboxylic and dicarboxylic acids. All of these are paramagnetic with a moment value of 1.74 μ_B approximately. Their composition may be represented by the general formula, Ag^{II}(XH₂)₂ (where XH₂ = one molecule of the tricarboxylic acid), two of the -COOH groups of each ligand remaining free.

There are no copper^I salts of pyridine tricarboxylic acids known, analogous to the silver complexes. The X-ray powder patterns of the two varieties of silver^{II} complex of 2:4:6-tricarboxylic acid of pyridine have been found to be different. There is no definite evidence whether this difference is due to the *cis-trans* isomerism of one and the same compound, as one of them (chocolate) contains one molecule of water of hydration and the other is anhydrous. All the silver^{II} complexes of tricarboxylic acids of pyridine are possibly represented by a monomeric structure like that of the argentic picolinate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The argentic complexes of pyridine tricarboxylic acids are formed by persulphate oxidation of silver nitrate in the presence of the acid concerned, exactly in the same way as in the cases of the previously described acids (cf. Banerjee and Ray, *loc. cit.*).

1. *Argentic Pyridine-2:4:6-tricarboxylate*.—Pyridine-2:4:6-tricarboxylic acid was prepared by the oxidation of collidine with potassium permanganate solution on the water-bath (Voigt, *Annalen*, 1881, 228, 31).

For the preparation of its argentic complex pyridine-2:4:6-tricarboxylic acid (0.8 g.) in a finely divided state was added to sodium persulphate (3 g.), dissolved in minimum quantity of water, and almost simultaneously a solution of 0.3 g. of silver nitrate in 10 c.c. of water was added to it. As before, silver nitrate and the acid should not be allowed to come in contact in the absence of persulphate, in order to avoid the formation of insoluble silver^I salt. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred by a magnetic stirrer for 3 hours. The colour of the solution gradually turned green.

(a) *Black form*.—If the reaction is continued at a temperature near about 25°, fine black crystals of the argentic complex separate from the green solution. The product was filtered through a sintered glass Gooch, washed with cold water till free from sulphate and then dried in a vacuum desiccator, placed in a refrigerator; yield 0.7 g. In all the other properties it resembles the argentic dipicolinate. [Found: Ag (oxidimetric), 20.50; Ag (gravimetric), 20.72; C, 36.41. Ag(C₈H₄NO₆)₂ requires Ag, 20.45; C, 36.36%]. $\chi_{225} = 2.24 \times 10^{-3}$; $\chi_{1369} = 1369 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_B = 1.816$.

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Fig. 1

Argentic Collidinate, Black

Fig. 2

Argentic Collidinate, Chocolate

(b) *Chocolate form*.—This was prepared as above with the reaction temperature maintained at about 15°. The mixture turned dark green with the separation of fine chocolate crystals. The yield and properties are almost the same as those of the black variety. [Found: Ag(oxidimetric), 19.43; Ag(gravimetric), 20.04; C, 35.70. Ag(C₅H₄NO₆)₂.H₂O requires Ag, 19.78; C, 35.16%]. $\chi_2 = 2.19 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_1 = 1394 \times 10^{-6}$ $\mu_1 = 1.832$.

X-ray.—The two differently coloured modifications of argentic collidinate (pyridine-2:4:6-tricarboxylate) show different structures, possibly caused by their difference in hydration. In this case also (cf. silver dipicolinate, *loc. cit.*) there is no evidence, however, to prove that they might be related as *cis-trans* isomers of one and the same compound. The powder X-ray photographs of the two silver⁺ collidinates are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. Tables I and II summarise the results of measurement of the X-ray lines of the black and chocolate collidinates.

TABLE I
Argentic collidinate, Ag (C₅H₄NO₆)₂.
(Black).

θ .	d .	Visual intensity.	θ .	d .	Visual intensity.	θ .	d .	Visual intensity.
4°15'	10.3950	5	12°53'	3.4546	100	19°51'	2.2684	5
5°50'	7.5791	10	14°18'	3.1185	70	20°24'	2.2097	3
6°45'	6.5538	50	14°52'	3.0021	2	20°58'	2.1525	3
7°30'	5.9011	2	15°45'	2.8377	2	21°33'	2.0971	3
8°29'	5.2213	0.50	16°28'	2.7173	15	22°24'	2.0128	3
9°31'	4.65°9	0.25	17°57'	2.5043	40	24°21'	1.8681	10
10°30'	4.2267	0.25	18°33'	2.4211	7	25°40'	1.8180	7
12°22'	3.5964	100	19°12'	2.3422	7	26°10'	1.7561	40

TABLE II
Argentic collidinate, Ag (C₅H₄NO₆)₂.H₂O.
(Chocolate).

θ .	d .	Visual intensity.	θ .	d .	Visual intensity.	θ .	d .	Visual intensity.
4°35'	9.6397	50	15°13'	2.9345	0.25	25°30'	1.8192	15
6°17'	7.0380	50	16°12'	2.7609	45	26°19'	1.7374	10
8°28'	5.2316	50	17°43'	2.5311	3	27°25'	1.6728	2
9°39'	4.5951	40	18°49'	2.3983	0.25	28°55'	1.5930	20
10°26'	4.2535	15	19°33'	2.3019	45	29°31'	1.5634	1
11°37'	3.8253	5	20°21'	2.2149	25	30°32'	1.5161	20
12°22'	3.6251	100	21°00'	2.1493	45	31°25'	1.4777	5
13°30'	3.2995	40	22°29'	2.0142	3	32°70'	1.4488	5
14°24'	3.0973	40	23°24'	1.9394	40	33°30'	1.4124	20

The X-ray powder photographs of argentic collidinates were taken in the 9 cm Unicam camera as in the cases of dipicolinates and quinolinates (cf. Banerjee and Rây, *loc. cit.*).

2. *Argentic Pyridine-2:4:5-tricarboxylate*.—Pyridine-2:4:5-tricarboxylic acid was obtained by the oxidation of berberine with concentrated nitric acid (Weidel, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 410).

The silver^{II} salt of this acid was prepared in the same way as the argentic collidinate (salt of 2:4:6-acid). The stirring was continued in the cold, and the product was kept in a vacuum desiccator at about 5°. It forms beautiful orange-coloured micro-crystals, and shows all the properties of bipoisitive silver as found in the cases of previous compounds. Yield is almost the same as the argentic collidinates. [Found: Ag(oxidimetric), 18.01; Ag(gravimetric), 18.10; C, 32.27. Ag(C₈H₄NO₆)₂·4H₂O requires Ag, 18.00; C, 32.00%]. $\chi_g = 1.655 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_A = 1225 \times 10^{-6}$; $\mu_s = 1.73$.

3. *Argentio Pyridine-2:3:6-tricarboxylate*.—Pyridine-2:3:6-tricarboxylic was obtained by the oxidation of sodium quinaldinate with boiling potassium permanganate solution (Miller, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1916).

The silver^{II} complex salt of 2:3:6-tricarboxylic acid was prepared in the same way as argentic collidinate and berberonate (salt of 2:4:5-acid). With stirring, the reaction mixture gradually turned green, from which green crystals of the complex separated out. But the product was found to be very unstable as it rapidly turned yellow on removal from the oxidising medium. Hence, it could not be analysed completely, though the state of oxidation of silver was determined by estimating the metal both oxidimetrically and gravimetrically from one and the same sample of the washed and moist substance.

For analysis, the substance was treated as usual with KI in acetic acid solution and the liberated iodine was titrated with thiosulphate. The solution after titration was evaporated to dryness and the residue was decomposed with a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and nitric acid. The mixture was then diluted with water, filtered, and from the solution silver was estimated gravimetrically as silver chloride. [Found: Ag (oxidimetric), 0.09515 g. and Ag(gravimetric), 0.09421 g.].

A consideration of the properties of the silver^{II} complexes of pyridine mono-, di- and tri-carboxylic acids indicates that in the order of their stability they may be arranged as follows: Complex (mono) > Complex (di) > Complex (tri).

In each of these groups again, the stability somewhat varies with the relative positions of the carboxyl groups. In the case of monocarboxylic acids, however, Ag^{II} complexes of all the three acids (*ortho*, *meta* and *para*) are more or less equally stable. Among the pyridine dicarboxylic acid complexes of Ag^{II}, those of cinchomeronic (3:4), isocinchomeronic (2:5) and lutidinic acids are more or less equally stable and their stability is greater than those of dipicolinic (2:6) and quinolinic (2:3) acids. In the case of pyridine tricarboxylic acids studied, Ag^{II} complex of the 2:3:6-acid is very unstable, while those of the other two (2:4:6 and 2:4:5) acids are fairly stable. This variation of stability with increasing number of -COOH groups attached to the pyridine nucleus and with their relative positions might be attributed to the steric effect, hindering the formation of favourable planar configuration around the central metal atom.